

Employee Retention and Turnover in Pakistan's Private Retail Banking Sector: An Exploration of Key Influencing Factors

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Abstract

This study examines employee retention and turnover within the retail private banking sector in the Islamabad region of Pakistan. Drawing on insights from interviews conducted at A Bank, the findings reveal several factors contributing to employee dissatisfaction, including heavy workloads, inadequate staffing levels, managerial practices, perceived gender bias, and concerns regarding the fairness of promotion processes. Employee job satisfaction is strongly affected by work pressure and the absence of supportive leadership, while staffing shortages and gender-related issues influence the quality of service delivery. Despite these challenges, many employees choose to remain with the organization due to limited alternative employment opportunities and their familiarity with the work environment. The study highlights the need for targeted retention strategies to enhance employee satisfaction and retention and suggests that future research should explore effective solutions across diverse geographical contexts.

Introduction:

Background:

Since Pakistan's independence in 1947, the banking system has seen substantial transformations, typically impacted by socioeconomic and political unrest. Early on, the sector faced resource difficulties, a scarcity of experienced people, and low-quality services. Despite these problems, banks in Pakistan have proven critical to the country's financial stability and growth. This dissertation looks at the factors that influence staff retention and turnover in Islamabad's private retail banking sector, with a focus on A Bank. It seeks to comprehend the difficulties encountered by employees, such as heavy workloads, management behaviour, staffing shortages, gender discrimination, and promotion procedures. The study is motivated by worries about high turnover rates in the banking business, particularly at A Bank, and aims to uncover the barriers that cause employees to quit or stay.

The study's main aims and critical questions are outlined, along with the theoretical framework and research design adopted. By investigating the elements that influence employee happiness and retention, this study hopes to provide insights that can assist improve working conditions and lead policies to create a more supportive work environment in the banking sector.

Research Aim:

The purpose of this study is to examine the factors that influence staff retention and turnover in Pakistan's private retail banking sector, as well as to assess the impact of the work environment and job satisfaction on employee retention, in order to provide valuable insights for better workforce management and organisational stability.

Research Questions:

1. What factors influence staff retention in Pakistan's private retail banking business, and what drives employment turnover within a year?
2. What impact do work environment and job satisfaction have on employee retention in the banking industry?

Literature Review:**Employee Turnover:**

This section explains employee turnover and discusses its effects, notably in the banking business. Employee turnover occurs when employees voluntarily leave a company during a specified time period rather than being laid off, retired, or terminated. High turnover costs organisations a lot of money since it costs to hire and train new employees. As a result, firms seek to lower turnover rates in order to cut costs and enhance overall efficiency (Dharmawan et al., 2015).

In Pakistan's banking sector, high turnover is linked to factors such as abusive supervisor behavior, poor working conditions, and limited opportunities for career advancement (Saeed et al., 2014). This industry plays a crucial role in the country's economy by generating employment and providing financial support to businesses, individuals, and the agricultural sector (Mughal, 2015). However, high turnover, estimated at affecting 35% of banks, compromises service quality, customer focus, and employee motivation (Masood Hassan, 2019).

According to research, various factors contribute to turnover, including limited autonomy, reliance on superiors, long working hours, and barriers to professional development (Buchbinder, Wilson, Melick, & Powe, 1999). Employees leave their positions due to a lack of training and development, which increases turnover rates (Thomson, 2010).

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory delves deeper into the causes of employee happiness and dissatisfaction, distinguishing between motivational factors (such as success and recognition) and hygienic elements (such as corporate regulations, supervision quality, and working environment) that impact turnover. Motivating factors increase job satisfaction through job accomplishment, recognition, and possibilities for growth and advancement, whereas hygienic elements minimise unhappiness by providing employees' basic requirements (Skripak, 2016). The presence of hygienic aspects, while not directly contributing to satisfaction, is critical for avoiding dissatisfaction.

Job Satisfaction & Employee Turnover

Moving on, we investigate the complex relationship between work satisfaction and employee turnover. We emphasize the importance of addressing both extrinsic and intrinsic demands by discussing how elements such as monetary benefits, employment security, and organizational culture contribute to work satisfaction and thus influence turnover rates.

Employees want to meet their extrinsic and intrinsic requirements. Extrinsic demands can be met with monetary benefits, whereas intrinsic needs can be met by inspiring staff. Fulfilling extrinsic and intrinsic demands will increase employee work satisfaction while decreasing staff turnover (Mahdi et al., 2012). According to Mahdi et al. (2012), monetary benefits, job stability, and a positive organizational culture all contribute to employment satisfaction. As a result, these factors aid organizations in accomplishing long-term objectives, such as employee retention. According to Saeed et al. (2014), employee job satisfaction and turnover are highly related. Highly pleased employees are more likely to stay with the organization, whilst unsatisfied employees are more likely to leave. Similarly, Kessler (2014) has demonstrated that unsatisfied personnel are not loyal or devoted to the organization. As a result, organizations should focus on increasing job satisfaction in order to retain talented individuals and reduce employee

turnover. Employee emotions, behavior, and attitude in the workplace have been claimed to be critical for job satisfaction (Negash, 2004). Furthermore, the quality of work completed by employees reflects their level of contentment. According to Khan (2014), abusive management, stress, and an excessive workload reduce job satisfaction and increase employee turnover.

Work Environment & Employee Turnover

The third segment examines the effect of the work environment on employee turnover. Inadequate working conditions, organizational uncertainty, and the level of effectiveness are investigated, offering light on how a positive work environment might impact an employee's decision to stay or quit.

Employees will not be willing to put up with a problem for a long time if working conditions are inadequate if the workplace lacks key accommodations such as basic lighting, furniture, restrooms, and other health and safety provisions. (SUMON.anti & SHAMSUZZOH) Organizational uncertainty has been linked to a high level of turnover. Employees are more likely to stay when the work environment is predictable, and vice versa (Zuber, 2001). There was a high level of personnel turnover in organizations with a high level of ineffectiveness (Alexander et al., 1994). For an employer, losing a significant employee may lower the likelihood of plan achievement and financial confidence in the company. Salaries, working conditions, and workplace safety are the primary drivers of turnover. Turnover is primarily caused by employee dissatisfaction. Employees on the other side are likewise under pressure to leave their current jobs owing to dissatisfaction. (Shamsuzzoh&Sumon.anti).

Employee Retention

In this section, we look at the essential idea of staff retention and its ramifications for businesses, particularly in the service sector and the ever-changing banking industry. In a study, Hom and Griffeth (1995) defined retention as the practice of motivating personnel to stay for an extended period of time or until the project is completed. According to Wysocki, B (1997), "The Society of Human Resource Management" believes that employee retention is the most recent problem in the current context.

Employee retention has not only become a concern for organizations in the current era, but it also poses a significant financial risk. Managing this phenomenon is critical for all sorts of organizations, particularly those in the service sector, because it has a direct relationship with their clients. The turnover impact and pattern would fluctuate from one industry to the next, but the service sector is more essential. Turnover should be decreased in all industries because it reduces productivity and output.

There is a need to create and implement a complete plan and tactics to attract, develop, and retain employees in the long term (Shahid, 2017). Customer service quality is critical in the service industry, and bank employees play an active part in providing excellent services to consumers. Stavrou-Costea (2005) contends that successful HR practices are the foundation for employee retention and finds a substantial relationship between HR practices and employee retention. According to Abeysekera (2007), an organization can reduce employee turnover by applying effective HR practices. Tripathi et al. (2011) aimed to evaluate the issues confronting professional institutions, both private and public, as well as the variables that can help them overcome these challenges. An investigation of both private and governmental institutions was done for this study, with an emphasis on factors such as job satisfaction, the work environment, working hours, reasons for job changes, faculty loyalty, tenure of service, and retention measures. Pay discontent, a lack of professional progression opportunities, an unpleasant work environment, job instability, and loyalty were recognized as major factors impacting faculty sentiments towards their institutions. The report listed reasons for faculty members quitting

their current jobs and what motivated them to stay. Gary Dessler and Biju Varkkey noted in their discussion of a comprehensive employee retention strategy that once retention concerns are identified, efforts can be taken to improve employee retention. Implementing pay hikes, making wise recruiting decisions, engaging in career conversations, providing guidance, offering flexibility, implementing appealing employee welfare measures, adopting HR techniques for high performance, establishing enforceable contracts, and other activities may fall under this category. As new technology and concepts such as e-banking, internet banking, and computerized accounting are launched on a daily basis, the banking sector has grown as one of the fastest-growing sectors in the current modern century.

Examining the influence of technological advancements, we explore how innovations such as e-banking and internet banking have reshaped the banking sector, affecting employee behavior, needs, and decisions to stay or leave the organization (Farooq & Hanif, 2013; Hong et al., 2012). These technological advancements have an impact on personnel as well. Employee behavior, needs, demands, training requirements, and remuneration all changed in reaction to these developments. All of these factors influence employees' decisions to remain or quit the organization (Farooq & Hanif, 2013; Mohsin et al., 2020a). According to (Hong et al., 2012; Naeem et al., 2020; Naseem et al., 2012), in the current world, human resources are the most valuable asset in any organization and are regarded as the organization's backbone. As a result, an organization must retain its staff in order to stay on track. As a result, organizations employ various ways to satisfy their employees' aspirations in order to retain their greatest personnel. According to M. Heathfield (2005), keeping talented personnel allows the organization to gain a competitive advantage that other competitors cannot match. Exploring the impact of globalization, we address how greater migration of talented individuals has contributed to an increase in personnel turnover, providing a substantial issue for organizations seeking to retain top talent (Kanwal and Majid, 2013; Samuel, 2008).

Job Satisfaction & Employee Retention

Moving on to a more in-depth analysis, we look at the relationship between job satisfaction and employee retention using Herzberg's motivational theory. We investigate the impact of job satisfaction on staff motivation and productivity, as well as its significance in determining bank success (Herzberg, HBR; Jasra et al., 2011). Job satisfaction is a critical component that influences employee motivation and productivity in any organization (Locke 2019). Job satisfaction is important in influencing the quality of customer service, operational efficiency, and overall success of banks (Vroom, 2014). Excessive workload and job stress are significant factors that reduce job satisfaction among bank personnel. According to a study published in the International Journal of Business and Management, job stress was the second most significant issue affecting job satisfaction among bank employees in Pakistan, with 33% indicating job stress as a major concern (Mubeen et al. 2013). According to Jasra et al. (2011), human resources have a significant impact on employee work happiness, and job satisfaction has a good impact on employee retention. According to Qualification, the most essential human resource management areas to motivate and retain personnel in the organization are staff selection and rewards and recognitions, training and development, work design, and job definition.

In Pakistan, Rehman et al. (2007) specified job satisfaction strategies such as salary, training, and promotion. They classified income, training, and promotion as having a significant and positive impact on employee work satisfaction. As a result, most employees place less emphasis on training than on compensation and promotion.

Work environment and Employee Retention

Continuing our investigation, we look into the impact of the work environment on employee retention. Long working hours and good communication between employees and employers are explored, demonstrating their significant impact on retention (Kanwal and Majid, 2013; Ahmada et al., 2015; Nasir and Mahmood, 2016). According to Ahmada et al. (2015), staff retention in Pakistan's banking sector is highly influenced by recognition and annual performance review. The survey also recommended that management create more flexible working hours and a safer working environment in order to retain staff. Other researchers (Patel and Patel, 2014) discovered that the work environment had a major impact on employee retention. Nasir and Mahmood (2016) conducted study on employee retention factors in Pakistan and concluded that work-life balance, job satisfaction, work environment, recognition, and supervisor support are all strongly connected to employee retention.

Research Methodology:

This section describes the study's objectives and methods. It describes the chosen sample, as well as the procedures of data collection and analysis, and addresses any ethical concerns or restrictions.

In-depth interviews, a widely recognised qualitative research method, served as the major methodology for this study. This strategy entailed conducting one-on-one interviews with each participant, allowing for a more focused investigation of individual perspectives. This strategy, distinguished by its conversational tone, enabled a thorough grasp of employees' perspectives and experiences. It was chosen because it may provide detailed insights into employees' motivations, difficulties, and general perceptions.

Qualitative research delves deeply into real-world issues by focussing on individuals' experiences, attitudes, and behaviours (Moser and Korstjens, 2017). Unlike quantitative research, which collects numerical data and applies interventions or treatments, qualitative research focusses on understanding the "how" and "why" of occurrences. It aids in the development of hypotheses and supplements quantitative data by providing richer, more nuanced information. In this study, a qualitative approach was chosen to gain a better understanding of people's experiences with unemployment, as well as their beliefs and emotions, because it allows for a more personal and meaningful exploration than a quantitative approach, which is broader and more numerically orientated.

To attain this level, in-depth interviews were used as the major data collection strategy. This well-known qualitative technique involves one-on-one conversations with participants, allowing for a focused investigation of each respondent's point of view. The conversational character of in-depth interviews allows for a thorough examination of the participants' perspectives and experiences, making them an excellent choice for this study. According to Kvale (1996), an interview is fundamentally a discourse between two people about a common theme or issue, which serves as a platform for mutual understanding.

Semi-structured interviews were employed in this study to elicit participants' different perspectives, experiences, and opinions. This method provides flexibility because the interviewer follows a defined framework of subjects while allowing the conversation to flow naturally based on the participants' responses. According to Rubin and Rubin (2005), good interviews combine primary questions with follow-ups and probes to ensure a full examination of the issue. To help with this, an interview guide was created, which served as an informal grouping of topics and questions that could be tailored to the responses of different participants (Lindlof and Taylor, 2002).

The unique research goals prompted the decision to use semi-structured interviews rather to

other data collection methods such as questionnaires. According to Drever (2003), the methodology used should be appropriate for the type of understanding sought. Given that the goal of this study was to offer a thorough picture of individuals' unemployment experiences rather than to generalise findings over a large population, semi-structured interviews were deemed most appropriate. This strategy allows for a more in-depth, case study-style investigation of the topic, focussing on individual experiences and generating insights that a more structured approach, such as questionnaires, may have missed.

Data Collection & Analysis:

To begin data collection, I contacted all participants via email and phone to explain the research objectives and schedule interviews. The participants requested that the interviews be done in their homes, which created a more relaxed environment and fostered openness about the research issue. Prior to the real study, participants were given a mock interview to familiarise themselves with the process and check that the questions were straightforward and did not create discomfort. The substance of the practice interview was not included in the final analysis. During the official interviews, all participants were asked the identical questions about their experiences.

The interview questions were open-ended, allowing participants to freely express their views and emotions. For example, a significant open-ended question stated, "How do your interactions with managers, coworkers, and superiors influence your decision to stay or leave?" Such enquiries allowed participants to delve further into the subtleties of their experiences, which was especially useful when dealing with difficult themes. Open-ended questions also helped to obtain rich, detailed information relevant to the research topic (Sarantakos, 1988). Throughout the interviews, care was taken to utilise clear and accessible language so that all participants could understand the questions (Bryman, 2001).

After the interviews were done, the data was transcribed and analysed. The transcription method not only functioned as a record, but it also helped the researcher gain a better grasp of the subject through repeated listening and examination of the transcripts. Following transcription, the data was coded with keywords to help categorise and organise the information, which is an essential component of qualitative research (Sarantakos, 1998).

Thematic analysis was used to uncover patterns and themes in the dataset. This iterative procedure included a constant analysis of the transcripts to identify recurring themes and make linkages between participants' responses. The coding method resulted in the classification of data into various themes and sub-themes, each allocated a unique code. The discovered themes highlighted both similarities and variations in participants' experiences, which were critical for interpreting the results. To confirm the validity and reliability of the findings, member verification and peer debriefing were used. These strategies included examining the data with participants to ensure accuracy and discussing interpretations with peers to increase the credibility of the analysis. Furthermore, ethical concerns such as protecting participant confidentiality and assuring voluntary involvement were prioritised throughout the research procedure.

Finally, the verification stage involved a complete examination of the recordings, transcripts, and codes to check that the interpretations were correct and aligned with the data. This enabled the researcher to check or, as needed, refine the themes and insights discovered throughout the study (Sarantakos 1998).

Findings & Discussion:

The research questions for a strong multiple-case study were carefully designed to address the study's primary problem and goal. The first question looks into the factors that influence employees' decisions to stay in their existing roles in Pakistan's private retail banking sector or

look for other opportunities within a year. The second question looks at how much the work environment and job satisfaction affect employee retention in the banking industry. Following full approval, participants were emailed a consent form, which was formally requested to be returned throughout the interview process. To safeguard participants' privacy, code names ranging from interviewee 1 to interviewee 10 were employed. The study's use of "A bank" as an identifier for the firm helped to safeguard the confidentiality of participants and organisational entities.

The information gleaned from the interviews and diary notes indicates not only the issues that participants face, but also the enablers that inspire and empower them to persevere in the face of these hurdles. Simultaneously, it sheds light on the factors pushing particular individuals to leave their employment in Pakistan's private retail banking sector, giving in a comprehensive picture of the dynamics influencing employee decisions in the industry.

The outcomes of the study done at A Bank in the Islamabad Region indicated numerous key themes linked to factors impacting employee turnover and retention in Pakistan's private retail banking sector.

Workload Challenges: According to George and Zakkariya (2015), role stress has a substantial impact on personnel in the banking industry, with important factors being job overload, role ambiguity, role stagnation, and role remoteness. Job stress in Pakistan's banking business is caused by a variety of issues, including work-family conflict, position ambiguity, inadequate rewards, and heavy workloads. Ahmed and Ramzan (2013) examined the impact of role ambiguity on job satisfaction and identified it as a major source of job stress in banks. Their data indicate that when job stress rises, job satisfaction falls.

During conversations with employees in the banking sector, workload challenges appeared as a consistent issue. Employees in various jobs commonly reported feeling overwhelmed by job responsibilities. Both long-term and newer employees experienced constant pressure to satisfy service expectations, which frequently resulted in longer working hours and higher stress levels. Daily duties, which required multitasking and continual decision-making, posed considerable hurdles to keeping a consistent work rate. The stress of managing various obligations, such as fulfilling high goals and meeting customer expectations, contributed to an unmanageable workload.

Furthermore, staff shortages exacerbated the situation by reducing service quality and disturbing employees' work-life balance. The requirement to balance sales targets with administrative chores worsened an already high workload, posing a significant barrier to job satisfaction. These reports underline the broad impact of workload demands at different levels within the banking sector, underlining the vital need for effective workforce management measures to increase worker satisfaction and retention.

Management Behaviour: According to Pietersen and Omi's (2014) research, the banking industry worldwide has high worker turnover due to inadequate assessment and delayed career advancement. Herzberg's classic motivation-hygiene theory (Herzberg, Mausner, & Snyderman, 1959) suggests that intrinsic motivators contribute to job satisfaction. Motivators include the nature of the work itself, recognition, autonomy, a sense of success, and opportunities for personal growth and advancement. They fulfil desires for success, competence, prestige, personal worth, and self-actualization. Job dissatisfaction, on the other hand, arises from a poor attitude towards "hygiene factors." Hygienic factors include compensation, job security, working environment, business policies and administration, supervision, and interpersonal relations. They are unrelated to the job and can generate dissatisfaction if an individual has negative affective reactions to one or more of them. Herzberg (1968).

The interviews shed light on the importance of managerial behaviour in shaping employees' work experiences in the banking industry. Employees commonly expressed how management behaviour affected their job satisfaction and the overall work environment. Several respondents emphasised the stress generated by high service expectations, emphasising the need for supportive management methods when coping with such difficulties. The Operations Manager emphasised the delicate balance required for effective decision-making, as well as the importance of managerial behaviour in creating a positive work environment. The Relationship Executive emphasised the challenges of meeting sales targets, emphasising the significance of management understanding and setting realistic expectations. Furthermore, both the Customer Relations Officer and the Relationship Manager emphasised the importance of management in addressing personnel shortages and promoting a healthy work-life balance. These findings emphasise the critical role of management behaviour in shaping the overall work experience, and they imply that supportive and empathic management practices are required to enhance job satisfaction and retention in the banking industry.

Staffing Issues: The interviews showed significant personnel difficulties in the banking industry. Employees frequently raised difficulties such as insufficient personnel levels, which resulted in increased strain and stress. The combined experiences highlighted the effect of staff shortages on service delivery quality, work-life balance, and overall job satisfaction. The anecdotes demonstrated widespread concern across various professions, emphasising the need for comprehensive solutions to people issues in the banking industry.

Gender Discrimination and Harassment: Women have struggled to work in organisational hierarchies in the banking sector, yet concerns like as glass ceilings, organisational culture, and stereotype acts continue to keep women under-represented in high-level positions (Kamkatwong and Kleiner, 2001). Furthermore, despite having comparable education and experience, women were barred from obtaining top executive positions in 1990 due to the workplace glass ceiling (Parker, Pascall, and Evetts 1998).

The detailed testimonials provided by employees, mainly women, shed light on the widespread impact of gender discrimination and harassment in the banking sector. According to Aroosh and Khalid (2014), women employees in Pakistan's banking sector have long suffered injustice against themselves, resulting in inequities such as the glass ceiling, gender compensation disparity, lack of reward, isolation, sex segregation, and sexual harassment. Men hold high executive positions in the banking industry and other organisations, whereas women face discrimination, and banks and organisational cultures do not support women (Aroosh and Khalid, 2014). Gender disparity is a major issue in Pakistan's labour market, and it is well documented, with women earning less than their male colleagues. The wage gap was 63.27 in 1979 and 33.09 in 1986 (Aftab and Sabir, 2007).

Female employees expressed a wide range of emotions, including frustration, disillusionment, and even dread, as a result of being treated unfairly because of their gender. The prevalence of such instances contributes to employee unhappiness with the job. The reported incidents of harassment exacerbated these emotions, creating an environment in which female employees felt vulnerable and unsupported. These detailed anecdotes emphasise the important need for organisations to address gender issues by building a workplace culture that prioritises equality, respect, and the well-being of all employees, regardless of gender.

Promotion methods: The interviews delve into the nuances of banking promotion methods, providing insights from employees in a variety of jobs. Participants expressed concerns about the transparency and fairness of promotion processes, with several identifying instances where promotions appeared to be influenced by factors other than merit and performance. A key

source of dissatisfaction was a lack of established criteria and information about promotional opportunities. Employees discussed how perceived favouritism and uncertainty in promotion methods influenced their job satisfaction and motivation. These findings emphasise the importance of open and merit-based promotion methods in the banking industry for enhancing employee morale and fostering a healthy organisational culture.

Graphical Representation of Key Challenges

The graph demonstrates the frequency and severity of various factors that affect employee turnover intentions and retention. The x-axis lists the factors, while the y-axis lists the values or scores. Based on the information provided, here's an interpretation:

Workload Difficulty: 4

Management Style: 2.

Gender Discrimination: 1. Staffing Issues: 2. Promotion Practices: 4.

The values on the y-axis show each factor's perceived influence or frequency. For example, both "Workload Challenges" and "Promotion Practices" receive a 4 rating, suggesting that employees believe these factors have a considerable impact on turnover intentions and retention. "Staffing Issues" received the lowest score of one, indicating that it may be perceived as less relevant in contrast. This graph displays the perceived importance of these attributes, with higher scores indicating a greater influence on turnover intentions and retention.

When asked if they had ever contemplated leaving their current position, and if so, what reasons influenced their decision to stay.

Several respondents pondered leaving their jobs, but their decision to stay is mostly motivated by a perceived lack of opportunities in the job market. Despite recurrent workload concerns, the Service Ambassador values the familiarity and comfort of the current job, emphasising the broad network and contacts built up over time. The Operations Manager, despite the hardships of the job, decides to stay since she is aware that banking professionals are routinely hired by competitors, and she is familiar with the current organisational culture and individuals. While dealing with sales targets, the Relationship Executive takes comfort in the established ties and predictability of the current work environment. Managing manpower shortages, the Customer Relations Officer is guided by the belief that the banking sector's close-knit community frequently travels between institutions, resulting in a preference for the known over the unknown. The Relationship Manager is committed to the current workplace due to a perceived lack of better options and a sense of comfort derived from the existing organisational culture

and connections. These comments highlight the significance of expected prospects, familiarity, and comfort in influencing employees' decisions to stay in the banking profession.

Conclusion:

As a result of this research, a comprehensive picture of the problems faced by banking professionals has emerged. In-depth interviews were used to investigate the subtleties of workload constraints, gender discrimination, promotional processes, and staffing issues. The examination of employees' ideas about quitting their jobs acted as a watershed moment, showing a complex network of factors influencing their behaviour. The considerable ratings awarded to "Workload Challenges" and "Promotion Practices" match to Herzberg's concept of "motivators," (Fig 2), indicating that these factors are considered as essential contributors to job satisfaction and motivation. "Staffing Issues," on the other hand, with a lower score, may be associated with hygiene factors—elements that, when lacking, generate unhappiness but, when present, simply result in a neutral environment. The overall trend in the graph emphasises the significance of Herzberg's approach in understanding the intricate interplay of factors influencing employee turnover and retention. This conclusion emphasises the need of addressing motivators like as workload and promotion policies in the banking industry, while also acknowledging the role of hygiene variables such as staffing shortages in maintaining a baseline.

Limitations:

Despite its important findings, this study has certain flaws that should be addressed. Although beneficial, the very tiny sample size is geographically restricted to a certain area of the banking sector. Furthermore, the study's focus on a single geographical and industry environment may limit its findings' applicability to a broader organisational or sectoral context. The inclusion of self-reported data increases the likelihood of response bias, since people may produce socially desirable responses or be influenced by recollection errors. While the study's qualitative character provides extensive narrative information, it may lack the statistical robustness associated with quantitative methodologies. Furthermore, while retaining confidentiality, the anonymity provided to participants limits the ability to link findings to specific job functions or organisational structures. Finally, the study's cross-sectional design covers a single point in time, making it impossible to detect patterns or changes in employee perceptions over time. Recognising these restrictions is crucial for interpreting the study's findings, and it recommends future research opportunities to alleviate these constraints and provide a more full understanding of turnover and retention dynamics. Also, the study focusses solely on employee opinions, but integrating the perspectives of management and other stakeholders could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the difficulties confronting the banking sector.

Further Research:

Further research on employee turnover and retention in banking organisations could look into a range of ways to better understand this complex topic. To begin, a larger-scale, longitudinal study including multiple A Bank branches and localities would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and dynamics that influence employee attrition. Such research might include a wide range of job roles and hierarchical levels, allowing for a more in-depth look at how these factors influence turnover rates and retention strategies.

Second, a quantitative study that combines survey-based data collection with objective performance measurements may offer more statistical rigour. Researchers could identify statistically significant trends and connections by quantifying parameters such as workload, job satisfaction, and perceptions of workplace culture, allowing for a more evidence-based approach to examining turnover causation.

Furthermore, analysing the effectiveness of specific retention tactics utilised by A Bank or comparable institutions may be beneficial. This could include a comprehensive review of policies controlling task management, career advancement, diversity and inclusion, and recognition and awards. Comparative examinations with other banks or financial institutions may shed light on industry best practices.

Furthermore, future study should examine the impact of technological advancements and digitisation on employee satisfaction and retention in the banking industry. As technology improves, the changing nature of work may present new challenges and opportunities for employee engagement and job satisfaction.

References

- Aftab, H. (2012). *A Study of Job Satisfaction and Its Impact on the Performance in the Banking Industry of Pakistan*. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(19).
- Aftab, Z., & Sabir, M. (2007). *Dynamism in the Gender Wage Gap: Evidence from Pakistan*. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 46(4), 865-882.
- Ahmed, A., & Ramzan, M. (2013). *Effects of job stress on employee's job performance: A study on the banking sector of Pakistan*. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 11(6), 61–68.
- Ahmada, N., Tariqb, M. S., & Hussain, A. (2015). *Human resource practices and employee retention, evidence from the banking sector of Pakistan*. *Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7, 186-188.
- Abeyssekera, R. (2007). *The impact of human resource management practices on the marketing executive turnover of leasing companies in Sri Lanka*. *Contemporary Management Research*, 3(3).
- Bryman, A. (2001). *Social Research Methods*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Dharmawan, A. H., Affandi, M. J., Hubesi, A. V., & Rusdi, M. (2015). *Employee Turnover Intentions in Indonesian Banking*. *International Journal of Information Technology and Business Management*, 38(1), 31-36.
- Drever, E. (2003). *Using Semi-structured Interviews in Small-Scale Research: A Teacher's Guide*. Glasgow: the SCRE Centre, University of Glasgow.
- Farooq, S., & Hanif, N. (2013). *A Descriptive Study of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivational Factors and Their Role in Employee Retention in the Banking Sector (Lahore) Pakistan*. *International Journal of Innovative and Applied Finance*, 1(1). Retrieved from <http://cls.irp.edu.pk/index.php/ijiaf/article/view/44>
- George, E., & Zakkariya, K. A. (2015). *Job-related stress and job satisfaction: A comparative study among bank employees*. *Journal of Management Development*.
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. B. (1959). *The Motivation of Work (2nd Ed)*. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- Herzberg, F. (1968). *One more time. How do you motivate employees?* *Harvard Business Review*, 46(1), 53–62.
- hibob. (n.d.). *What is Employee Retention Rate?* Available at: <https://www.hibob.com/hr-glossary/employee-retention-rate/> (Accessed: 8 January 2024).
- Hom, P.W., & Griffeth, R.W. (1995). *Employee turnover*. Cincinnati, OH: South-Western.
- Hong, E. N. C., Hao, L. Z., Kumar, R., Ramedran, C., & Kadiresan, V. (2012). *An effectiveness of human resource management practices on employee retention in institute of higher learning: A regression analysis*. *International Journal of Business Research and Management*, 3(2), 60-79.
- Huning, T. M., & Thomson, N. F. (2010). *The impact of performance attributions and job satisfaction on turnover intentions*. In *Allied Academies International Conference*. Academy of

- Organizational Culture, Communications, and Conflict*. Proceedings (Vol. 15, No. 1, p. 27). Jordan Whitney Enterprises, Inc.
- Jasra, J. M., Khan, M. A., Hunjra, A. I., Rehman, R. A. U., & Azam, R. I. (2011). *Determinants of business success of small and medium enterprises*. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(20), 274-280.
- Kamkatwong, S., & Kleiner, B. H. (2001). *Discrimination in the financial industry*. *Equal Opportunities International*, 20(5/6/7), 70-73.
- Kanwal, A., & Majid, M. (2013). *Retention Management in the Banking System: An Evidence from Multan, Punjab Pakistan*. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(1), 795-804.
- Kariuki, P. W. (2015). *Factors affecting employee turnover in the banking industry in Kenya: A case study of Imperial Bank Limited*. Project Report Submitted for Masters in Organizational Development United States International University.
- Kessler, L. L. (2014). *The effect of job satisfaction on IT employees' turnover intention in Israel*. *Annals of the University of Oradea, Economic Science Series*, 23, 1028-1038.
- Kim, S., Tam, L., Kim, J.-N., & Rhee, Y. (2017). *Determinants of employee turnover intention*. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 22(3), 308-328.
- Khan, M. A. (2014). *Organizational cynicism and employee turnover intention: Evidence from the banking sector in Pakistan*. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce & Social Sciences*, 8(1), 30-41.
- Kvale, S. (1996). *An Introduction to Qualitative Research Interviewing*. London: Sage Publications. *Interviews*:
- Locke, E. A. (2019). *What is job satisfaction?* *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 4(4), 309-336.
- Mahdi, A. F., Zin, M. Z. M., Nor, M. R. M., Sakat, A. A., & Naim, A. S. A. (2012). *The relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention*. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(9), 1518-1526.
- Masood Hassan, T. S. (2019). *Employee turnover in public sector banks of Pakistan*. McGregor, D. (1960/2006). *The Human Side of Enterprise*, annotated edition, McGraw-Hill.
- Moser A, Korstjens I. (2017). Series: *Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 1: Introduction*. *European Journal of General Practice*, 23(1), 271-273.
- Mumtaz, R., & Hasan, S. S. (2018). *Determinants of Employee Turnover: A Survey of Employee Intentions Trend in Urban Societies of the Region*. *Business and Economics Journal*, 9(2), 1-8.
- Nasir, S. Z., & Mahmood, N. (2016). *Determinants of Employee Retention: An Evidence from Pakistan*. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(9), 182-194.
- Negash, M. (2004). *The Effects of Job Satisfaction on Employees' Turnover Intention in Addis Ababa Branches, Wegagen Banks Co*. Retrieved from <https://docplayer.net/62227830-The-effects-of-job-satisfaction-on-employees-turnover-intention-in-addis-ababa-branches-wegagen-bank-s-co-by-mekonnen-negash-addis-ababa-university.html>
- Patel, N. R., & Patel, M. B. (2014). *To Study the Impact of HR Practices on Employee Retention" - a Case Study of L & T Ltd, Hazira, Surat*. *Indian Journal of Research*, 3(8), 98-100.
- Peters, T. J., & Waterman, R. H. (2006). *In Search of Excellence*. Sydney: Harper Business. Price (1977). *Keeping Good Teachers*. *Educational Leadership*, 60(8), 1-10.
- Pietersen, C., & Oni, O. A. (2014). *Employee Turnover in a Regional Commercial Bank*. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(27).
- Price, J. L. (1977). *The Study of Turnover*. Ames, Iowa: Iowa State University Press.
- Rehman, K. U., Zaheer, B., & Sufwan, N. (2007). *A Study Measuring the Effect of Pay*.

- Reina, C. S., Rogers, K. M., Peterson, S. J., Byron, K., & Hom, P. W. (2018). *Quitting the Boss? The Role of Manager Influence Tactics and Employee Emotional Engagement in Voluntary Turnover. Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 25(1), 5-18.
- Rubin, H. J., & Rubin, C. S. (2005). *Qualitative Interviewing: The Art of Hearing Data (2nd Ed.)*. California: Sage Publications.
- Samuel, M. (2008). *Using motivational strategy as a panacea for employee retention and turnover in selected public and private sector organizations in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. Master of Commerce in Industrial Psychology in the Faculty of Management and Commerce, University of Fort Hare.*
- Sarantakos, S. (1998). *Social Research*. Hampshire: PALGRAVE.
- Saeed, I., Waseem, M., Sikander, S., & Rizwan, M. (2014). *The relationship of turnover intention with job satisfaction, job performance, leader-member exchange, emotional intelligence, and organizational commitment. International Journal of Learning and Development*, 4(2), 242-256.
- Shahid, A. (2017). *Strategies Used by Banking Managers to Reduce Employee Turnover*, Walden University.
- Shamsuzzoha, & Shumon. (2010). *Employee Turnover-a Study of its Causes and Effects to Different Industries in Bangladesh. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science [Special Issue - July 2012]*.
- Stavrou-Costea, E. (2005). "The challenges of human resource management towards organizational effectiveness: A comparative study in Southern EU." *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 29(2), 112-134.
- Tripathi, B. K., Kshama Ganjiwale, & Babita Agarwal (2011). *Faculty retention- A strategic tool for winning competitive edge. Tecnia Journal of Management Studies*, 5(2), 91-100.
- Vroom, V. H. (2014). *Work and Motivation*. Wiley.
- Weigold, I. K., Porfeli, E. J., & Weigold, A. (2013). *Examining tenets of personal growth initiative using the personal growth initiative scale-II. Psychological Assessment*, 25(4), 1396-1403.
- Wysocki, B. (1997). *Retaining employees turns into a hot topic. Wall Street Journal, September 8, B1.*
- Zin, M. Z. M., Nor, M. R. M., Sakat, A. A., & Naim, A. S. A. (2012). *The relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(9), 1518-1526.